
SciMesh

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Contents:

1	Status of this document	2
1.1	Todo list	2
2	SciMesh at a glance	3
2.1	Introduction	3
2.2	Current scope of SciMesh	4
2.3	Data model overview	5
3	SciMesh vocabulary	6
4	Prototype: JuliaBase	6
4.1	Give it a try!	7
5	Note about content addressing	7
6	Implementation	9
6.1	Workflow	9
6.2	Good URIs	9
6.3	Authentication	11

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Abstract SciMesh is a set of specifications that define the representation of scientific results in form of a knowledge graph. While many such data formats focus on simulation data, SciMesh explicitly includes physical specimens as first-class citizens. Thus, provenance of both data and specimens can be documented. SciMesh's immediate purpose is to represent content of electronic lab notebooks (ELNs) for sharing scientific results across ELN instances. This way, collaboration partners running different ELNs (even different ELN software) can have a uniform view on their collective results without media disruptions.

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1 Status of this document

This is a work in progress, which, once finished, is supposed to be a gentle introduction into SciMesh as well as a reference for it.

It is also a “request for comments”. Thus, if you want to contribute ideas or content, or if you found a mistake, don’t hesitate to get in touch.

1.1 Todo list

Without significant ordering:

- Add further triplets to the RDF output, even it makes it highly redundant. For example, inverse relations like “is_specified_input_of” are interesting. There are probably tons of vocabulary to investigate, especially in the OBO ecosystem.
- Create proper entities for people (operators, “currently responsible person” of a sample). Currently, only a string literal containing the login name is emitted.
- Highly JuliaBase-specific: Create proper entities for sample topics.
- The current scheme has no persistent way to identify a sample. (This may turn out to be an implementation detail as JuliaBase does have a persistent identifier for each sample.)
- Find a way to deal with sample renames.
- Currently, most predicates are home-brew (i.e., they use our URI). They should be replaced with existing, widely adopted third-party URIs wherever possible.
- We should assure that the kind of properties is clear, either by using an established predicate or by other means. Eventually, a re-using party must be able to derive that e.g. a temperature is a temperature.
- Connect process classes (in other words, experimental methods) with third-party entities representing the underlying method(s).

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2 SciMesh at a glance

2.1 Introduction

SciMesh represents scientific insights as a knowledge graph. In its current realisation, it focuses on sample-based workflows, in which samples (physical ones or data artefacts) undergo a sequence of processing and measurement steps. However, it is not limited to that. Most generally, it represents scientific insight by declaring a relationship between cause and effect. In other words, *if* certain prerequisites are set, *then* certain observations will be made.

Fig. 2.1: Example graph of processes.

Fig. 2.1 shows a graph illustrating this line of thought. Starting from an initial state called “nil”, processes change this state. There is a monotonic increase in time from left to right. Consequently, this time axis also is inherent in a chain of processes. A process may be “take glass substrate out of rack”, “heat sample”, “mix two substances together”, or “wait for solar eclipse”. It is really that general. Every process has got one or more parents. If it is a single one, it may be the initial state. The initial state is totally void. It bears no information at all, which is why the chain of processes must define the states in-between as completely as necessary to be useful for scientific conclusions. Conversely, one process may be the parent of multiple others. This way, chains can be branched off, possibly by different scientists years after the work on the main trunk.

Fig. 2.2: Example graph of processes, showing cause and effect.

Fig. 2.2 shows how the essence of scientific work, the relation of effects to causes, is represented in the graph: The processes up to a certain point are the cause, and the observations at

that point are the effect. Therefore, it is valid to call that point an “insight”, which is a graph node of its own. Two things are important here. First, the process to which the observational data is attached is a measurement, and quite frequently, a measurement does not change state. Still, it is a process proper, with all bells and whistles. We think that it is not necessary to distinguish between measurements and processes which actually change something. Besides, a measurement does change state, albeit the change may not be significant. And secondly, a certain graph of processes might have many insights pointing to it. In particular, the processes following a measurement may lead to a second measurement with new results, meaning a new insight.

Fig. 2.3: Is-a relations of insight-like entity classes.

Speaking of insights, Fig. 2.3 shows the relationships of things that may point to a certain state (a.k.a. process) in a graph. All of them are *insights* but if it is about a chain of concrete processes at certain points in time, this should be labelled as an *experiment*. If all of this happened to the same sample, the experiment may be identified with this *sample*.

If the processes are not concrete but generic blueprints of processes, the experiment is actually a *recipe* for experiments. Or, by bringing cause and effect together, it is a scientific *hypothesis*.

To illustrate experiment versus hypothesis, consider the following two examples, respectively:

1. On 21 October 2019, John jumped from the Eiffel Tower, and he moved downwards.
2. A body is released in a gravitational field, and it moves according to the force field.

2.2 Current scope of SciMesh

The currently specified RDF data model of SciMesh is narrower than the very general concept outlined above. The reason is very simple: Our work is in its early stages, and we have to focus on specific domains of research in order to avoid frittering away our resources. Since we work in task area “Caden” of NFDI4Ing, the domain of research of choice are sample-based workflows.

We hope to be able to give guidelines for how to extend SciMesh to other domains, eventually.

2.3 Data model overview

The RDF data model is build around two concepts: *Sample* and *process*. Both are meant in their broadest senses. A sample may represent a state of a physical specimen as well as a data set. A process may create a new sample state (i.e., change the sample, for example an etching process), or create new data (e.g. a measurement on a sample), or both.

Simplified example topology of a SciMesh knowledge graph. Colours denote namespaces: Blue is the ELN namespace, green is the SciMesh namespace, and red are external namespaces (RDF, OWL, OBO etc).

Fig. ?? gives an overview of the anatomy of a knowledge graph in SciMesh. It is a very simple graph yet contains most of the basic concepts. At its heart, there is a sequence of processes (at the bottom) that work on the sample. The first process, “substrate”, creates the sample (the sample starts its life as a bare substrate). Its RDF properties determine the basic physical properties of the sample (e.g. material and size). Then, further layers of material are deposited on the substrate in the deposition process. Common properties of most processes are name, method, timestamp, operator, and comments.

Note that three different namespace domains are involved:

1. The domain of the ELN instance: the processes, the process types, the sample and its intermediate instances. This is in blue.
2. The domain of the ELN software: the sample type. This is in green.
3. External domains like BFO/OBO and RDF. This is in red.

Note: Some may have noticed a striking resemblance to Git’s data model. Indeed, there is a very close mapping possible between both. The processes are commits, and the sample is a branch. You may split a sample in half, creating a new branch. At the same time, one process may have more than one parent. This way, pouring two chemical substances corresponds to merging in Git.

3 SciMesh vocabulary

Namespace: <http://scimesh.org/SciMesh/>

Process (class) A process in the sense of Fig. 2.1 and Fig. 2.2.

Insight (class) An insight in the sense of Fig. 2.1 and Fig. 2.2.

Experiment (class) A specialised insight (see Fig. 2.3) which represents a concrete experiment. It points to a graph of equally concrete processes, i.e. processes that happened at a certain place at point in time, with certain ingredients and result state and/or observational results. Normally, all such processes bear a timestamp.

Hypothesis (class) A specialised insight (see Fig. 2.3) which represents a general hypothesis, in contrast to a concrete experiment. It points to a graph of non-concrete processes which represent a sequence of generic state changes and observations.

Recipe (class) A specialised insight (see Fig. 2.3) which represents a general recipe, in contrast to a concrete experiment. It points to a graph of non-concrete processes which represent a sequence of generic state changes.

Sample (class) A sample (see also Fig. 2.3), which may be a physical specimen as well as a simulation result artefact. It is represented by the process it points to, and all of its ancestors. This process chain may also contain process *after* the sample. Those are not part of the sample.

parent (property) This contains a parent of the subject in the object. Both subject and object are of type “Process”.

The object may also be `rdf:nil`. In this case, it must be the only parent.

finalState (property) This connects an insight to the latest process of its process chain. If the insight is a sample, the latest process represents the current state of the sample.

4 Prototype: JuliaBase

JuliaBase is a Python/Django framework for creating ELNs, or same databases, with a high degree of customisability. Because it realises a process/sample-based workflow in a highly-structured manner, it is a good candidate for prototyping SciMesh.

Fig. 4.1 shows a simple sample data sheet. In chronological order, you can see what has been done with the sample. In this case, only one thing: The “5-chamber deposition” is the only experiment here. It consists of three layers of silicon which have been deposited on the substrate, each with its setup configuration (temperature, gas flow rates).

Although this sample data sheet is so simple, its RDF representation is rather complex, see Fig. 4.2. This RDF is in turtle format, which is human readable (well, with some experience). After the namespace prefixes (the lines that start with `@prefix`), which serve merely to abbreviate common prefixes with very short names, you can see the sample with its properties, living in the `jb-s` namespace. The `parent` property points to the last process made with this sample.

Sample "14S-005"	
Currently responsible person: Rosalee Calvert	
Topic: Cooperation with Paris University	
Current location: Rosalee's Office	
is amongst My Samples: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
5-chamber deposition	Rosalee Calvert, 2014-10-02 16:10:00
Deposition number: 14S-005	
Layer number: 001	SiH ₄ : 4 sccm
Layer type: p	H ₂ : 1 sccm
Chamber: p	Silane conc.: 70.59 %
Temperature: 158/165 °C	
Layer number: 002	SiH ₄ : 3 sccm
Layer type: i	H ₂ : 0 sccm
Chamber: i2	Silane conc.: 100 %
Temperature: 113/172 °C	
Layer number: 003	SiH ₄ : 9 sccm
Layer type: n	H ₂ : 11 sccm
Chamber: n	Silane conc.: 32.93 %
Temperature: 133/158 °C	

Fig. 4.1: Data sheet of sample "14S-005", as seen in a JuliaBase instance by the browser.

This process is the only one at the same time (`sm:parent: ()`). It is the deposition process. It ends with the empty line. By the way, the instance-specific entities (in other words, the things that are special for the respective institute like the experimental methods) live in the namespace `ns1`.

What follows is the first layer with its data. It links to its deposition with the `jb:isSubprocess` property. The data of the second layer and the complete third layer are elided here for clarity.

4.1 Give it a try!

The prototypical implementation is kept in sync with this document. It is made against the JuliaBase software in its `graphs` branch. There is also a [short howto](#) for getting RDF data out of a JuliaBase test instance.

5 Note about content addressing

"Content addressing" means naming a content after its ... well ... content. By using the checksum of the content as the name, name and content become one. This is the most persistent identifier for data you can get. No ambiguities, no manipulations.

Such identifiers can be used to cite an element of a SciMesh graph. For example, one can cite a SciMesh insight in a paper. Or, one can use such identifiers in a blockchain to document absolutely reliably that a certain scientist made a certain discovery at a certain point in time.

The previously mentioned Git, for example, uses hash values for naming each commit. Those hashes are not random: They are the checksum of the current source tree content, and *all*

```

@prefix jb: <http://juliabase.org/jb#> .
@prefix jb-s: <http://juliabase.org/jb/Sample#> .
@prefix ns1: <https://inm.example.com/FiveChamberLayer/> .
@prefix jb-p: <http://juliabase.org/jb/Process#> .
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .
@prefix s.o: <https://schema.org/> .
@prefix sm: <http://scimesh.org/SciMesh/> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .

<http://inm.example.com/samples/14S-005> a <https://inm.example.com/Sample> ;
  jb-s:currentLocation "Rosalee's office" ;
  jb-s:currentlyResponsiblePerson <https://inm.example.com/User/7> ;
  jb-s:name "14S-005" ;
  jb-s:topic "Cooperation with Paris University" ;
  sm:parent <http://inm.example.com/5-chamber_depositions/14S-005> .

<http://inm.example.com/5-chamber_depositions/14S-005> a sm:Process,
  <https://inm.example.com/FiveChamberDeposition> ;
  rdfs:label "5-chamber deposition 14S-005" ;
  jb-p:comments "" ;
  jb-p:finished true ;
  jb-p:timestamp "2014-10-02T14:10:00+00:00"^^xsd:dateTime ;
  sm:parent () .

ns1:13 a <https://inm.example.com/FiveChamberLayer> ;
  jb:isSubprocess <http://inm.example.com/5-chamber_depositions/14S-005> ;
  ns1:number 1 ;
  ns1:chamber "p" ;
  ns1:sih4 [ a s.o:QuantitativeValue ;
    s.o:unitText "sccm" ;
    s.o:value 4.000 ] ;
  ns1:temperature1 [ a s.o:QuantitativeValue ;
    s.o:unitCode "CEL" ;
    s.o:unitText "°C" ;
    s.o:value 158.000 ] ;

ns1:14 a <https://inm.example.com/FiveChamberLayer> ;
...

```

Fig. 4.2: Turtle representation of sample “14S-005”.

changes that have led to this content. So, the complete history of a project is encoded into the commit's name. This way, one cannot tamper with a Git repository without changing all names, too. Conversely, if I refer to a certain Git commit by its name, I can reliably check that I got unmanipulated content. Content addressing at its best.

Similar methods are used in IPFS or various (all?) blockchains.

However, in an RDF triplet store, you can change anything as you like at any time (given you have the necessary permissions).

In order to get content addressing in SciMesh, one may capture a snapshot of a SciMesh graph in IPLD. IPLD would return a name for it, which will be persistently linked to that graph with exactly that content. However, this method has never been tried so far, so for the time being, content addressing and immutability in SciMesh should be considered future tech.

6 Implementation

The following gives best practise and normative requirements for how to implement SciMesh at an institution, in particular, in an ELN or samples database.

6.1 Workflow

Fig. 6.1 shows the bouncing of samples and data between two institutes working together. The problem at hand is the experimental activities with sample #1, which is created in Institute A, but also investigated in Institute B. At the same time, it is necessary to be able to look at *all* data in *both* institutes.

The text-heavy figure contains most of the detail. Therefore, I will only make some remarks in the following.

Both institutes have their own ELN. Those two ELNs are not only different instances on different computers; they may even be different software.

It is important to see that Institute A is the “real” home of the sample since the URI of the sample is actually a URL in the domain of Institute A. However, there is a URL (*not* URI) for sample #1 at Institute B. Any party needing to collect all data of sample #1 must poll both URLs. Instances may deliver data also found at other instances but this is not guaranteed.

Institute A keeps a list with all URLs that also have data of sample #1, and exports it as part of the SciMesh graph of sample #1.

Two aspects are not covered at all in this graphics: caching and permissions. While the first is an optional yet important optimisation, the latter is essential and will be covered later.

6.2 Good URIs

We recommend to follow the guidelines explained in “[Cool URIs for the Semantic Web](#)” when you create URI of any kind, but in particular for samples and processes. Moreover, you may

Institute A with ELN A

create sample #1
with URI `http://A/samples/1`

do things with sample #1 and
record them in ELN A

send sample physically to Institute B

add URL of sample #1 in ELN B
to ELN A

ELN A responses with the SciMesh graph
for sample #1

open the data sheet for sample #1

ELN A makes an HTTP GET request
against the URL, requesting
an RDF content-type

*ELN A shows the data from ELN A
and ELN B together in one data sheet*

Institute B with ELN B

add sample with URI `http://A/samples/1`
to ELN B

send URL of sample #1 in ELN B to Institut A

open the data sheet for sample #1

ELN B makes an HTTP GET request
against the URL to that URI, requesting
an RDF content-type

ELN B shows the data from ELN A for sample #1

do things with sample #1 and
record them in ELN B

ELN B responses with the SciMesh graph for
the activities with sample #1 at Institute B

open the data sheet for sample #1

*ELN B shows the data from ELN A
and ELN B together in one data sheet*

Fig. 6.1: Possible workflow for two institutes working together with the same samples.

or may not use any of the ubiquitous PID (persistent identifier) services out there, some of which are specialised to physical samples.

In any case, URIs of samples and processes must be URLs at the same time that yield the corresponding SciMesh graph via HTTPS. (Note that the URI should start with `http://`, though.)

6.3 Authentication

Scientific data might be sensitive for a couple of reasons. Anyway, an ELN will generally refuse to deliver knowledge graphs without authentication and authorisation.

Currently, SciMesh-compliant ELNs must implement the following method of authorisation, called “mutual trust”.

Mutual trust

Fig. 6.2: Trust graph for the “mutual trust” method.

This method is very simple. The ELN instance contains a list of peering ELNs that it trusts. In practise, this trust is established by a bilateral agreement between the managements of the respective institutions.

Technically, both ELN instances must send TLS client certificates at each HTTPS request, which are used to authenticate the ELN by the peer.

Note that this scenario does not mean that every scientist can access all data of the peer ELN. It only means that the ELN instance can access all data on the peer ELN, but in general will show only a subset of it to the scientist.

Fig. 6.2 shows the underlying trust graph. As said, both ELNs trust each other, and the scientists trust their respective ELN.

Discussion of other methods

Fig. 6.3: Trust graph for the "personal trust" model.

The "mutual trust" may seem to be all too trustful. Therefore, let's have a look at a more restricted option.

Fig. 6.2 shows an alternative trust graph. Here, the ELNs do not need to trust each other. Instead, they trust certain scientists of the other institute.

It is not easy at all for an ELN to implement this. Since no data must be relayed through the peer ELN (which we don't trust), the sample data sheet with the joint data needs to be compiled in the browser by JavaScript or WebAssembly code (or a proxy web service, for that matter) that can be trusted by the scientist not to forward any data to third parties, in particular, not to the ELN of the scientist's own institute.

This does not make much sense, given that the scientist and the ELN is under the very same governance, therefore, SciMesh does not include an authorisation method for such a trust model for the time being. It may make sense, however, if at least one of the ELNs provides its service to scientists of different institutions (governances).